

(REVIEW ARTICLE)

The use of TikTok social media with dating behavior: A literature review

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World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2025, 25(02), 305-311

Publication history: Received on 23 December 2024; revised on 31 January 2025; accepted on 03 February 2025

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2025.25.2.0336>

Abstract

Introduction: Adolescents experience significant changes in physical, emotional, and social aspects, including in dating behavior. Some forms of dating behavior, such as kissing, necking, petting, and intercourse, have the potential to increase the risk of premarital sexual intercourse among adolescents. In addition, the use of social media such as TikTok also influences the mindset and behavior of adolescents, including in relationships. Therefore, this study aims to analyze the use of TikTok social media with dating behavior in adolescents.

Method: The research design used in this paper is a literature review with 10 journals, 3 international journals and 7 national journals.

Result and Discussion: Of the ten articles used in this literature review, some of them shows that there is a significant influence of TikTok social media on dating behavior.

Conclusion: TikTok can have a positive or negative impact depending on how it is used, so awareness and control are needed in its use to minimize adverse effects on adolescent behavior.

Keywords: Adolescents; Social media; Tiktok; Adolescent behavior; Dating behavior

1. Introduction

Adolescence is a transitional period between childhood and adulthood characterized by various physical, emotional and psychological changes. At this stage, adolescents experience rapid development, both in biological and social aspects. However, this development process also makes adolescents more vulnerable to various problems, especially those related to deviant behavior. One of the problems that often arise is risky dating behavior, which can lead to premarital sexual behavior.

According to WHO, adolescents are individuals aged 10-19 years, while according to the National Population and Family Planning Agency (BKKBN), the age range of adolescents is 10-24 years old and unmarried (1). Data from the Central Statistics Agency (BPS) in 2020 showed that the Indonesian population aged 15-24 years reached 44.2 million people or 16.5% of the total population (2). This large number shows that adolescents have an important role in nation building, but also face various challenges, especially those related to reproductive health and sexual behavior.

Various studies have shown that adolescent dating behavior in Indonesia is increasingly leading to risky activities. Research by Saroh et al. (2022) revealed that most adolescents engage in physical activities in dating, ranging from hand holding (93.3%) to sexual intercourse (7.6%) (3). Furthermore, the 2018 BKKBN survey reported that 74% of men and 59% of women had had sexual intercourse before marriage, with a peak at the age of 17 (19%) (4). This behavior can

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lead to various negative impacts, such as unwanted pregnancies, abortions, sexually transmitted infections, and increased rates of early marriage.

Factors that encourage risky dating behavior include the lack of knowledge of adolescents about reproductive health and the negative impact of premarital sexual behavior. Based on data from BAPPENAS, 2017, adolescent knowledge is obtained by 55.3% who have low knowledge about reproductive health and 30% of adolescents' knowledge about the time of the fertile period is also still low (Ertiana and Ottu, 2020) (5). This low knowledge can increase adolescents' curiosity, making them more vulnerable to risky sexual behavior.

In addition to internal factors, external factors such as exposure to social media also have a role in shaping adolescent behavior. Social media, such as TikTok, Instagram, and YouTube, provide wide access to various information, including content that can influence adolescents' socio-sexual behavior. Mashuri's research (2020) showed a relationship between social media use and adolescent dating behavior (6), while Winarti and Andriani's research (2019) revealed that the use of Instagram social media is related to promiscuous sexual behavior in adolescents of SMA Negeri 5 Samarinda (7).

2. Material and methods

The research method used in this research is the literature review method. The journals used in this study are national and international journals. The journals reviewed in this study totaled 10 journals from 7 national journals and 3 international journals. Data searches in the research were carried out by searching from sources such as journal portal websites that can be accessed such as Pubmed, Google Scholar and others. The articles used adjust to the search keywords related to the literature review.

3. Results

Ten articles— seven in Indonesian and three in English—have been reviewed and analyzed as follows.

Table 1 Results of Review of 10 Articles

No	Author	Research Title	Location	Method	Subject	Result
1	Ainul Muthemainnah., <i>et al.</i> (2022)	The Influence of Tiktok Media on Adolescents' Knowledge of Premarital Sexual Behavior at SMAN 3 MAROS	SMAN 3 Maros	This study used a quantitative approach with a one-group pre-post test design. Using total sampling	The research subjects were 28 students from SMAN 3 Maros.	The study showed a significant difference in the level of knowledge regarding premarital sexual behavior among secondary school students before and after health promotion through TikTok, with a p value of 0.000, indicating a strong effect of TikTok on students' knowledge. The mean knowledge score increased from 4.82 to 8.42 post education, showing a significant improvement. The majority of students (71.4%) fell into the "sufficient" knowledge category after the intervention. This study concludes that TikTok is an effective medium to improve adolescents' understanding of premarital sexual behavior.

2	Khaerunnisa, <i>et al.</i> (2019).	Analysis of the Influence of TikTok Social Media Use on Adolescent Behavior in the Community Environment	In Sawakong Village, which is located in South Galesong District, Takalar Regency, South Sulawesi	This research uses a quantitative approach with a descriptive type to analyze the influence of TikTok on adolescent behavior.	100 individuals aged 10 to 24 years old.	The study showed a significant effect of TikTok use on adolescent behavior in Sawakong Village, with a Pearson correlation value of 0.775 and a significance value of 0.000, indicating a strong relationship between TikTok users and adolescent behavior.
3	Via Fransiska. (2019).	The Influence of TikTok Application Use on Teenagers in the 4.0 Era	-	It uses library research methodologies, collecting data from a variety of primary sources such as books, journals, and previous studies	The subject of the research paper mainly focuses on the influence of the TikTok application on adolescents in the context of the 4.0 era	The findings suggest that TikTok can have both positive and negative effects on teens, requiring caution for underage users regarding the content they consume.
4	Riswanda Maulana, <i>et al.</i> (2024).	TikTok Trends: Unraveling Teen Behavior in the Digital Age	Japanese Village, in Gempol Pasuruan Regency	qualitative methods such as observation, interviews, and documentation to gather insights from youth	teenagers in Kejapanan Village who are TikTok application users	The study identified four prominent behaviors among teens who use TikTok: impulsive spending influenced by viral trends, the Fear of Missing Out (FOMO) phenomenon in fashion, selective digital literacy, and a tendency to judge others. TikTok serves as a powerful platform for the dissemination of information and digital literacy, but it also fosters consumptive habits and judgmental attitudes among users. These findings emphasize the need for responsible use of social media to reduce potential negative impacts on personal and social well-being.
5	Eka Wanda S. (2022).	Perilaku Sosial Pengguna Tiktok (Studi Pada Siswa SMA Negeri 8 Makassar)	SMA Negeri 8 Makassar	This study uses a qualitative descriptive methodology. Data collection techniques include observation, interviews, and documentation	students of SMA Negeri 8 Makassar, especially classes X and XI	Research revealed that the social behavior of students who use TikTok at SMA Negeri 8 Makassar is characterized by individualism, where students are reluctant to accept the opinions of others, and apathy, which includes ignoring friends during conversations and a lack of

						willingness to help each other.
6	Sri widianingsih, <i>et al.</i> (2022).	Relationship of Tiktok Social Media Usage with Teenagers' Sexual Behavior at Smpn 7 Samarinda	SMPN 7 Samarinda	This study uses a quantitative research methodology with a cross-sectional design. Selected using stratified random sampling from a total population of 633 students	97 respondents from grades VII and VIII	The study did not find a significant relationship between TikTok social media use and adolescent sexual behavior during the pandemic at SMPN 7 Samarinda. The results showed that the majority of respondents who used TikTok had a high level of sexual behavior, with 76 respondents (78.4%) engaging in sexual behavior that was categorized as free. In contrast, 13 respondents (13.4%) were categorized as not engaging in promiscuous sexual behavior. Statistical analysis showed a p value of 0.970, indicating no significant correlation between TikTok use and sexual behavior among adolescents
7	Septi Maisyaroh Ulina.P., <i>et al.</i> (2024).	The Relationship Between the Use of Social Media TikTok and Premarital Sexual Behavior in Adolescents at SMP N 8 BATAM	SMP N 8 Batam, which is located in Hang Lekiu, Sambau, Nongsa District, Batam City, Riau Islands, Indonesia	This study uses a quantitative methodology with a cross-sectional approach. Purposive sampling techniques	56 respondents were selected using the purposive sampling technique.	The study found a significant association between TikTok use and premarital sexual behavior among seventh-grade students at SMP N 8 Batam, with a p value of 0.009, showing a strong correlation. Among the respondents, 57.1% were active TikTok users, and 53.6% indicated risky premarital sexual behavior. The analysis revealed that active TikTok users are 4.4 times more likely to engage in risky premarital sexual behavior compared to passive users. The findings point to the need for educational interventions to address sexual behavior among adolescents.
8	Lian Tang, <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Influence Of Tiktok Usage Toward Positive Emotion and Relationship	TikTok users in China	The research uses a quantitative approach using the survey method	A total of 244 online questionnaires were distributed, with 177 respondents	The study found that attitudes towards TikTok, specifically perceived usability and perceived ease of use, significantly influenced positive emotions and relationships among

					qualifying after eliminating outliers	users in China, contributing to 36.8% of the positive emotion variance ($R^2 = .368$) However, TikTok usage patterns do not predict positive emotions, with only the duration of use contributing to a statistically significant positive relationship ($R^2 = 0.054$) Additionally, demographic characteristics, such as monthly income, did not show significant differences in TikTok usage or its relationship with positive emotions
9	Michael R. Langlais, et al. (2024).	TikTok and Romantic Relationships: A Qualitative Descriptive Analysis	major universities in the Southeastern U.S.	The study uses a qualitative descriptive design	64 participants	The study identified four main themes regarding how emerging adults use TikTok in the context of romantic relationships: relationship initiation, viewing relationship content, sharing content in relationships, and posting relationship content. Participants also noted that TikTok usage could lead to potential conflicts within relationships. The thematic analysis results were elaborated in a table, indicating a structured presentation of findings
10	Elena Bozzola, et al. (2024).	The Use of Social Media in Children and Adolescents: Scoping	-.	An electronic search was conducted on the PubMed database using specific search terms related to social media, health, and pediatrics.	Among children and adolescents, especially during the COVID-19 pandemic	Showed a significant association between social media use and adverse health outcomes, although causation could not be definitively established.

4. Discussion

4.1. The Use of Tiktok Social Media With Dating Behavior

Based on a literature review conducted by researchers, it explains the use of TikTok social media with dating behavior. Research conducted by Michael, et al. (2024) respondents reported that TikTok can raise the standard of relationships and serve as a communication tool, while also leading to social comparisons and insecurities (8).

The study, titled influence of tiktok usage toward positive emotion and relationship, showed results noting that excessive use of TikTok can lead to negative emotional outcomes and strained interpersonal relationships. Additionally, the study investigated the role of demographic characteristics, such as age, marital status, and education level, in

shaping TikTok usage patterns and their influence on users' emotional states and interpersonal relationships. on demographic characteristics, such as monthly income, did not show a significant difference in TikTok usage or its relationship with positive emotions (9).

Research conducted by Septi Maisyaroh Ulina.P., et al. (2024) showed that the study found a significant relationship between TikTok use and premaritalized sexual behavior among seventh grade students at SMP N 8 Batam, with a p value of 0.009, showing a strong correlation. Among the respondents, 57.1% were active TikTok users, and 53.6% indicated risky premarital sexual behavior (10).

Research conducted by Via Fransiska. (2019), Research shows that technological advances in social media, particularly TikTok, significantly affect how teens engage with online platforms. Positive outcomes include increased creativity, increased physical activity, and the development of new skills and knowledge. Instead, negative effects include wasted time, exposure to misinformation, social comparisons, and potential bullying (11).

Research by Khaerunnisa., et al. (2019), The findings show a significant correlation (Pearson correlation value of 0.775) between TikTok use and changes in adolescent behavior, highlighting the difficulty in distinguishing the educational value of viral content (12).

Research by Ainul Muthemainnah., et al. (2022), The study showed a significant difference in the level of knowledge regarding premarital sexual behavior among high school students before and after health promotion through TikTok, with a p value of 0.000, showing a strong effect of TikTok on students' knowledge (13).

Research by Elena Bozzola., et al. (2022), found the results of a scoping review analyzed 86 reports related to the negative impact of social media on children and adolescents, identifying key issues such as depression, anxiety, and body image issues. The review highlights that high levels of screen time and social media use correlate with a range of psychological problems, including addiction and body image misconceptions. It was noted that increased social media use was associated with increased mental health problems among adolescents, emphasizing the need for awareness and preventive measures. The findings suggest a significant link between social media use and adverse health outcomes, although the causes and effects cannot be definitively established (14).

There are differences in the research of Riswanda Maulana., et al. (2024), These findings underscore the need for responsible use of social media to reduce potential negative impacts on personal and social well-being (15).

Research by Eka Wanda S. (2022), This study concluded that the use of TikTok leads to reduced direct interaction, reduced cooperation, and loss of mutual respect among students (16).

Research by Sri widianingsih, et al. (2022), The findings revealed no significant relationship between TikTok use and adolescent sexual behavior, showing that the intensity of social media use was not correlated with sexual activity among respondents, Statistical analysis showed a p value of 0.970, showing no significant correlation between TikTok use and sexual behavior among adolescents (17).

5. Conclusion

The use of TikTok social media on dating behavior shows positive and negative impacts. TikTok can serve as a communication tool that increases interaction in relationships, enriches creativity, and provides education related to relationships and dating behavior. However, on the other hand, overuse can give rise to social comparisons, anxiety, and insecurity in relationships.

Some studies have shown a correlation between TikTok use and risky dating behaviors, such as premarital sex among teens, although other studies have found no significant relationship. TikTok also affects changes in adolescents' behavior, both in terms of emotional expression and the way they interact with their partners.

In addition, other negative impacts include reduced direct interactions, decreased mutual respect, and increased risk of exposure to content that can affect the perception of relationships. Therefore, the use of TikTok in the context of relationships needs to be done wisely so that the benefits can be optimized without causing a negative impact on dating behavior.

In conclusion, TikTok can have a positive or negative impact depending on how it is used, so awareness and control are needed in its use to minimize adverse effects on adolescent behavior.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

The authors acknowledge the reviewer's positive insights and suggestions in this paper.

Disclosure of conflict of interest

There is one finding that contradict the theory.

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